

Supplementary Material 1. Equations for EDA-Derived Variables

Total Area Under the Curve (AUC) from Baseline

After subtracting the participant's baseline mean (so baseline ≈ 0 μS), the Total AUC from baseline summarizes the net cumulative deviation of EDA over the analysis window (i.e., test period). Because it integrates across time, it captures both how much (i.e., duration) and for how long (i.e., magnitude) the signal deviates from baseline:

$$\text{Total AUC}_{\text{from baseline}} = \int_0^T EDA_{\text{norm}}(t) dt \approx \text{trapz}(EDA_{\text{norm}}(t_i), \Delta t)$$

where $EDA_{\text{norm}}(t)$ is the baseline-normalized EDA signal at time t (μS). Computed as raw EDA minus baseline mean; t is continuous time (s); t_i is discrete sample times used in trapezoidal integration (s); Δt is sampling interval, $\Delta t = 1/\text{sampling rate}$ (s); T is duration of the analyzed period (test window; s); and $\text{trapz}(\cdot)$ is the trapezoidal numerical integration operator (sums area).

As this variable reflects the net physiological activation (or suppression) during the SECPT relative to baseline: (i) positive AUC means that overall EDA was elevated compared to baseline (i.e., greater sympathetic-linked arousal over time); (ii) negative AUC means that overall EDA was suppressed below baseline; and (iii) $\text{AUC} \approx 0$ means that EDA returned quickly to baseline.

Sympathetic Activity

The Sympathetic Activity expresses the extent to which the total integrated response exceeded baseline, treating the area above baseline as a proxy for sympathetic activation. It normalizes the positive area by the sum of positive and negative areas, yielding an intuitive percentage.

This was calculated as:

$$\text{Sympathetic \%} = \frac{|AUC^+|}{|AUC^+| + |AUC^-|} \times 100$$

where AUC^+ is area where $EDA_{norm}(t) > 0$ (above baseline), integrated over time ($\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{s}$); and AUC^- is area where $EDA_{norm}(t) < 0$ (below baseline), integrated over time ($\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{s}$). As this variable reflects the sympathetic activation response during the SECPT, values closer to 100% mean a dominated sympathetic response; values below 50% mean a suppression/recovery response.

Stress Volatility

Stress volatility reflects the instability or irregularity of arousal over time, summarizing each overlapping window with an arousal index (A_t) of the (post-baseline/test) EDA in that window, then quantifying how erratically that index changes from one window to the next. With overlapping windows (default 30 s, 50% overlap; adaptively shortened for short signals), the arousal index is:

$$A_t = \mu_t + \sigma_t$$

where μ_t and σ_t are the mean and standard deviation of EDA within window t . Volatility is the standard deviation of first differences:

$$\text{Stress Volatility} = \text{std}(A_t - A_{t-1})$$

where std is the standard deviation across all first differences; $A_t - A_{t-1}$ is the first difference of the arousal index between adjacent windows. In this sense, high volatility means that arousal changes erratically, suggesting physiological instability or less stable regulation. Low volatility means that arousal changes smoothly, indicating stable regulation or a calm state.

Arousal Variability

Arousal Variability summarizes the extent to which physiological arousal fluctuates over time.

The analysis segments the test EDA into overlapping windows (default ~30 s with 50% overlap; adaptively shortened for brief recordings). Within each window, it forms an arousal index that combines both level and dispersion of EDA, then quantifies the spread of these indices across windows. Arousal variability is then the standard deviation of these indices across all windows:

$$\text{Arousal Variability} = \text{std}(\{A_t\}_{t=1}^N)$$

where $\text{std}(\{A_t\})$ is the standard deviation of the arousal index values across all windows, and N is the number of windows across the analyzed period. Higher variability indicates a more labile (less stable) arousal profile, and lower variability indicates steadier arousal over time.